

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NIYANG****FIRST NAME: PIRINGAR****PROGRAM CODE : DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show essential information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Starting the Essay (EUCLID 2021, 1)
2. Researching the Topic (EUCLID 2021, 1-2)
3. Organizing Your Ideas (EUCLID 2021, 2)
4. Rules of Thumb and Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 14-15; Blum 2011, 2; Thunder 2004, 493)
5. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35; Oluniyi and Olajumoke 2013, 1)
6. Retrospective cohort (Austin 2007, 61-64)
7. AFM (Austin 2007, 73)

WRITING EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC PAPERS

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401D first-semester course pack provides extensive guidance on how to write a quality academic article. In the coursepack's nine chapters, the authors condense their years of experience into clear, easy-to-follow descriptions of the steps necessary to write a winning academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 1). This essay is a brief overview of the most significant elements of the ACA-401 course pack that pertain to formal research and writing. In addition to shorter extracts and crib sheets from various sources in the appropriate style, the coursepack includes the whole text of Academic Writing for Graduate Students. Although there is a universally accepted style for academic writing, authors can choose between using American English, British English, or European Commission criteria for spelling, idioms, and punctuation.

2) **THE BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING**

Academic writing differs from business writing, journalistic writing, and other less formal forms in that it includes stricter guidelines for sentence construction, terminology, and references. This ensures a uniformly high writing standard throughout all articles by providing a consistent, easily recognizable structure for the reader. However, the standards for punctuation and grammar in academic writing are the same as in any other writing style (EUCLID, 2021).

While each academic institution may have different requirements for line spacing and headings, the format for titles and paragraphs appears consistent. The essential bit of style guidance in this respect is that the writer maintains uniformity in their use of American and British English linguistic variants (i.e., not mixing US and UK English in the essay). Examples include the Turabian Manual for Writers, which insists on using footnotes in addition to in-text citations, and the Chicago Manual of Style, which recommends using in-text citations exclusively.

a) Chapter one: Essay writing

The first chapter explains the three most essential steps in writing an essay: having an overview of the basics of essay writing, knowing the steps for creating a great essay, and knowing the rules of thumb for writing a paper. Only academic essays, such as theses, dissertations, and conference papers, are discussed in this chapter. This includes research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork that may be published in journal articles, books, newspaper articles, monographs, book or literature reviews, technical reports, student presentations, etc.

Writing also has to be done in a relaxed order, but there are standard procedures to follow when composing an academic essay. Before beginning the essay, the following procedures are recommended: Initiate writing as soon as feasible because delay is counterproductive. First and foremost, the writer must set aside sufficient time to read, study, consider, and write a draft. While it is vital to define and write down as much as one knows about a subject, analyzing and delivering the solutions to the question is even more crucial. Outlining how one intends to complete the essay is crucial. The first draft of an essay outline should incorporate the initial thoughts and ideas regarding the research issue and serve as a roadmap for your investigation. A well-written preparation for an essay will help figure out how to respond to the question and what sources to draw from.

The chapter also suggests editing the essay after completion and giving it some final thought from a new angle before submitting it. The chapter ended with some general guidelines for composing essays, which included the following:

Staying focused to avoid confusion, for example, there is no need to draw the leaning tower of Pisa to criticize Galileo's "falling body theory" the focus should be narrowed to just those components of Galileo's theory that have a direct bearing on the

writing to avoid unnecessary distraction, not starting or concluding with sweeping generalizations, writing clearly, ensuring that the writing is not dull or clumsy. The chapter also recommended that assertions should be supported, and views being discussed should be taken seriously.

b) Chapter two: Punctuations

In chapter two, punctuation is discussed in detail. The use of apostrophes, brackets, colons, semicolons, commas, dashes, hyphens, ellipses, periods, question marks, and quote marks are all covered in detail. This chapter posits that punctuation should be minimized as a general rule. The chapter goes on to provide much explanation on each of the punctuation marks, which are outlined below:

Apostrophe which is used:

- to indicate possession, e.g., Mercy's pen, the builders' association meeting
- to indicate location, e.g., St. Paul's cathedral
- to indicate contractions or omission of letters, e.g., do not contract to don't

The apostrophe should not be used to form plural words; e.g., "four oranges" is wrong. It should be written as "four oranges."

Brackets may be round, squared, curly, or angled. Round brackets are used to add more meaning to a word, e.g., the church (a place where Christians meet). Square brackets are used for enclosing references, comments, or corrections, e.g., According to John Bunyan [England, 1628]. Angle brackets and curly brackets are used for other technical purposes.

Bullet points are used to create a list of items. For example, the cast of "the tempest" include:

- Prospero
- Miranda
- Ariel
- Caliban

Worthy of note is the indication that there should be no punctuation after the bullet points. However, if it forms part of a starting sentence, a full stop should be added after the last point, while a semicolon should be added to each bullet point if each forms a complete sentence. This chapter explained all the punctuation marks to enable the writer to become familiar with all punctuation marks, learn the appropriate use of punctuation marks, and know the difference between correct and incorrect punctuation marks.

c) Chapter 3: American vs. British English

Chapter 3 is dedicated to the differences between American and British English covered in this chapter. It was clear that any version (either US or UK English) can be used in a written document, but ensuring consistency in use is of utmost importance once a preference has been made. The chapter explains that American and British English are similar but with some differences, such as:

Words that have the same pronunciation but different spelling, e.g., schedule

Words that have different spellings but the same pronunciation, e.g., plow (British) and plow (American)

Words that are the same but have different meanings. E.g., pants in British English mean underwear, while pants in American English mean trousers.

The chapter also elaborated on grammar, syntax, collective nouns, pluralized adjectives, euphemistic references, ethnolects, the influence of Jewish and Yiddish lexis and structure, and the use of jargon.

d) Chapter four: Plagiarism

In chapter four of the course pack, the issue of plagiarism is discussed at length (EUCLID 2021, 33-39). The author defines plagiarism and discusses how to properly reference sources through in-text citations, endnotes, or footnotes. The learner will learn the format and guidelines to be followed to improve his academic style and how to organize the list of Works referenced through examples. Plagiarism entails using the words or ideas of another person without providing proper credit to that person. Plagiarism would occur if you had someone else prepare a paper and turn it in to your professor under your name. The chapter explains how to avoid plagiarism by citing and paraphrasing and how to insert footnotes using MS word.

e) Chapter five: What is a style guide, and why would I need one?

In chapter five (EUCLID, 2021, 40-42), titled "What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One?" the importance of following a particular writing pattern. The chapter explains that different style guides are used in technical, business, journalistic, and web copywriting fields. However, the writer should be consistent when a writing style is chosen. The chapter explains that writing style should take cognizance of the recommended length of sentences, manuscript layout, font use, spellings (UK v US, for example), accepted terms, and required content.

f) Chapter six: CMS crib sheet

Chapter 6 (EUCLID, 2021, 43-57) covers the CMS Crib Sheet on Chicago Style and Usage, the specifics of the Chicago style, and familiarization with examples. Abbreviations (which are not commonly used within texts except in tables, references, notes, or in parenthesis), acronyms (which are introduced after writing the words in full for the first time), geographical terms (which include how to describe places), capitalization (which may be full caps, heading caps or sentence caps), internet language (such as emails that are primarily spelled in lower case), and compounds (which are multiple words that can work together). The chapter also includes an explanation of the appropriate use of italics, quotation marks, numerals, page formats, footnotes, headings, lists, tables, end notes, footnotes, and bibliographies in Chicago style are all covered in this chapter.

g) Chapter seven: Latin abbreviations and expressions

Latin expressions and abbreviations are explained in chapter seven (EUCLID, 2021, 58-64) of the course pack. The meaning of Latin abbreviations in writing was explained. As described in the text, Latin abbreviations can be used in various contexts, including footnotes, citations, and parenthetical references. However, to avoid confusion, the text recommends always using the full English term when writing formally, academically, or technically. For example, ante meridiem means before noon, in situ means in its original place, among other things, etc.

3) CONCLUSION

Academic writing has stricter guidelines for style, grammar, and punctuation. In addition to bolstering the author's authority, dedication to precision and consistency also helps the reader focus on the material at hand. To excel in academic writing, one must dedicate oneself to constant development as a writer and to increasing conceptual clarity. The materials in the course pack provide a graduate student with the context and materials necessary for composing academic works such as essays, scholarly articles, and dissertations. Students benefit from this instruction because it teaches them to identify writing, logic, critical thinking, accurate language, and proper style as hallmarks of academic reading, research, and writing.

REFERENCES

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